

Insights and Conclusions from Analyzing the Hungarian Bebras Initiative in 2021-2022

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Abstract. Empowering young people to become active agents in modern society and shape the world around them is a critical imperative for education. It is essential to inspire and equip them with the skills and knowledge to make a positive impact on their communities and the world at large. In addition, digital skills and computational thinking are crucial components of modern education that can enable young people to navigate an increasingly complex and technologically advanced world. Developing these skills can not only enhance their employability but also empower them to find innovative solutions to global challenges and drive positive change in society.

The Bebras initiative, with over 70 countries participating, is a successful approach to involving school students in computer science problem-solving and deep thinking. In Hungary, the Bebras challenge is conducted in cooperation with VILLE, and the results from 2021 were analyzed in detail. Further analysis was carried out on the 2021 and 2022 tasks separately, raising additional research questions that led to the development of a methodology and research project. The present study summarizes these analyses, along with the methodology and research project, and establishes additional research questions.

The methodology and the findings of this new research project can have an impact on the development of computer science challenges in the topic of problem-solving, and motivation in CS and CT and they can serve as a guide for future studies and analyses in this field.

Keywords: Bebras challenge, Computational Thinking, motivation in Computer Science, Computer Science education.

1 Introduction

Computational thinking (CT) is a crucial skill for all students in the 21st century, not just those pursuing computer science or mathematics. However, the concept can be complex and is often misunderstood as being narrowly related to computing or computers. [1] The significance of computational thinking has aroused the swift advancement of educational initiatives and programs dedicated to its cultivation. The development of students' computational thinking skills presents challenges in terms of its adaptability and emphasis across diverse educational environments, as it extends be-

yond the boundaries of programming and computer science, encompassing interdisciplinary aspects. [2]

Applying CT in education significantly enhances students' capacity for critical and analytical thinking, fostering their aptitude to think systematically and computationally. [3] Thinking computationally refers to the utilization of computer science principles for problem-solving purposes. This cognitive process encompasses the systematic decomposition of a problem into more manageable subcomponents, the identification and analysis of patterns and interconnections within the problem domain, the formulation of algorithmic representations or procedural instructions to address the problem systematically, and the critical evaluation of the solution's suitability and effectiveness in achieving the intended objectives.

1.1 The Bebras Challenge

The Bebras Challenge [4, 5, 6] is an international initiative aimed at promoting alongside the computational thinking (CT) the computer science and informatics among primary and secondary school students. The challenge consists of solving short concept-based tasks that are based on informatics concepts and can be answered in a few minutes. Organized annually for almost twenty years, the challenge has gained popularity in many countries as an informal school event. Participants in the challenge are usually supervised by teachers who may integrate the challenge into their teaching activities. The challenge is structured into six age groups, each with its own set of tasks: Pre-Primary (grades 1-2), Primary or Little Beavers (grades 3-4), Benjamins (grades 5-6), Cadets (grades 7-8), Juniors (grades 9-10), and Seniors (grades 11-12). Students solve 18 to 24 tasks in 45-55 minutes.

The Bebras Challenge aims to make informatics education more attractive for learners by providing problem-solving experience and insight into what lies beyond digital technology. [4] It provides a platform for students to showcase their abilities and compete with other participants from diverse schools and nations. This event enables them to connect with like-minded individuals and potentially form new friendships within their area of interest.

The Bebras Challenge, which has a strong resemblance to the CS unplugged methodology [7], is primarily conducted online. Its tasks are designed to be solved without the aid of a computer, promoting hands-on learning. The tasks are concise, engaging, and centered around fundamental computer science concepts, enabling students to comprehend the underlying principles behind technology. The CS unplugged methods are highly effective in providing students with a glimpse into another fascinating aspect of computer science - the inner workings of a computer. [4,6]

Overall, the Bebras Challenge is an excellent way to promote informatics education and CT among students, and it has been successful in promoting CT, as evidenced by the increasing number of participants each year. [8] The challenge's structure, which includes different age groups and sets of tasks, makes it accessible to a wide range of students, and its online format makes it easy to participate in from anywhere in the world.

1.2 The Bebras Challenge in Hungary

Since 2011, the Hungarian Bebras Challenge [7,8] has been running with the goal of promoting informatics and CT among students. The challenge aims to motivate students in exploring computing, develop problem solving and critical thinking skills, provide activities that can be done in classrooms without requiring computers, and suggest school and after-school activities to teachers.

The number of participants has been steadily increasing each year (see Fig.1), with students of various ages and schools taking part in the challenge. Participants are given 45 minutes to solve tasks online, with easy, medium, and hard levels of difficulty to choose from.

Fig. 1. The number of participants in the Hungarian Bebras challenge from 2011 to 2022.

Tasks are always presented in the same order based on their difficulty, and participants are allowed to switch between tasks while they compete. To prevent students from feeling discouraged by negative marks for incorrect answers, the Challenge awards bonus marks to all participants at the beginning.

In cooperation with Lithuania, Finland and India the Hungarian Bebras organizers started in 2021 a new project to use a learning analytics enriched environment, ViLLE [8]. The number of the participating countries was extended in 2022 with Sweden, Ireland, Spain, as well.

Multiple choice questions were used in the first year (2021), with four options. It was improved to use interactive tasks in 2022.

2 Analysis of the results of the Challenge in 2021-2022

2.1 Methods

We analyze the scores and the differences in scores between girls and boys every year. In addition to the descriptive statistics, the Independent T-test (on score's interval scale) is executed using SPSS.

When we analyzed the results in each task separately, our aim was only to analyze the students' success without being influenced by the task's difficulty level. So, we normed the results of the students for -1 (wrong answer), 0 (not answered), and +1 (correct answer) and ran Mann-Whitney tests in ordinary scales.

2.2 Success in the Tasks

2021.

In 2021, 33467 students participated in 5 age groups. There was no big difference between the number of girls and boys, only in the oldest age group (senior), where the difference between the number of boys and girls was more than two times. (See Fig. 2)

Fig. 2. The number of participants in the Hungarian Bebras challenge 2021 clustered by age groups and gender.

The first analysis showed significant differences between boys and girls only in the total scores of the two oldest age groups. (see Table 1)

	sex	N	mean	sd	t	df	p
Juniors	girls	5929	112.20	36.486	3.129	12459	<.001
	boys	6562	110.21	34.606			
Seniors	girls	808	89.06	28.193	5.690	1668	<.001
	boys	1976	96.00	31.590			

Table 1. descriptive statistics about Junior and Senior categories in 2021

Because of this first result, our deeper, task and gender separated analysis focuses on the 2 oldest age groups.

More descriptive analysis of the difficulty level shows that success in task-solving moves together in the case of girls and boys in both age groups. However, some can be seen some differences (see Fig.3 and Fig 4.).

Fig. 3. The means of the normalized results in the Hungarian Bebras challenge 2021 in Junior age group for the used tasks.

Fig. 4. The means of the normalized results in the Hungarian Bebras challenge 2021 in Senior age group for the used tasks.

To analyze deeper the tasks more separately we collected the tasks for each age group where significant differences in the success can be found (see Appendix A).

We used 25 tasks in these two age groups, and 13 tasks had shown a significant difference for girls in 4, and for boys in 9 cases.

We could not find a relationship between the significant differences and the difficulty level of the tasks. Some tasks were wrongly graded for difficulty level (see Fig 3

and Fig. 4), the number of correct solutions was higher (easier than graded) or lower (harder than graded).

In Junior level two tasks showed lower numbers in solutions, were harder as expected (2021-BE-02 and 2021-UZ-02) and showed significant differences. The other tasks that showed a significant difference were either easier or at an appropriate level of difficulty.

In senior level 3 easy, 2 medium and 2 hard tasks showed significant differences and except for one task (2021-PH-03), they were of the expected level of difficulty and performed according to their classification for the age group (see Fig.4).

If we can find significant differences in both age groups in the same tasks, the differences are for the same gender (boys). The 3 tasks showing significant difference for girls, and used in both age groups, didn't show differences in the oldest age group.

2022.

In 2022, 37350 students participated from 283 schools in 5 age groups in the competition. There was no big difference between the number of girls and boys. The highest difference can be found again in the oldest age group (see Fig.5).

Fig. 5. The number of participants in the Hungarian Bebras challenge 2022 clustered by age groups and gender.

For this year we created the same analysis as for the results in 2021.

In 2022 we have found a significant difference in the two oldest age groups between girls and boys again (see Table 2).

	sex	N	mean	sd	t	df	p
Juniors	girls	7018	80,71	34,306	13.734	13279	<.001
	boys	6265	89,32	37,970			
Seniors	girls	2189	65,86	30,608	5.861	4943	<.001

	boys	3493	70,92	33,372		
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Table 2. descriptive statistics about Junior and Senior categories in 2022

The descriptive analysis of the difficulty level shows again that success in task-solving moves together in the case of girls and boys in both age groups. However, some differences can be seen again (see Fig.6 and Fig.7).

Fig. 6. The means of the normalized results in the Hungarian Bebras challenge 2022 in Junior age group for the used tasks

Fig. 7. The means of the normalized results in the Hungarian Bebras challenge 2022 in Senior age group for the used tasks

To analyze deeper the tasks separately we collected the tasks for each age group where significant differences in the success can be found (see Appendix B).

Of the 24 tasks used in these two age groups, 13 tasks had shown significant difference for girls in 1, and for boys in 12 cases.

In the case of using a task in more age groups we can see significant differences not in all age groups, this year as well. We could not find a relationship between the significant differences and the difficulty level of the tasks.

Overall, the tasks in the Junior age category were poorly calibrated. In general, in terms of correct answers, the tasks were more difficult for the participants than expected.

Although most of the easy tasks in the Senior age category should have been rated as medium or difficult (see Fig. 6. and Fig. 7.), they did not necessarily show a significant difference between girls and boys. Only two tasks from 6 show significant differences and was harder as expected.

If we can find significant differences in more age groups in the same tasks, the differences are for the same gender.

3 New Research – Gender Texting Analysis

We identified and will discuss the features of tasks where the impact was more relevant, and where the difference showed significance.

Our next step in this research based on your analysis is to find whether the story or the texting of the tasks influence the success of students in these tasks.

3.1 Methodology

The determination of the gender of tasks was prepared a larger-scale study involving teachers and students (participants and not participants as well).

Data collection was conducted through an online survey.

In the first part of the survey the respondents are asked to provide their gender, age group, and whether they participated in the current competition that included the tasks in question.

The second part of the survey (see Fig. 8) utilizes a 5-point Likert scale to gauge the gender of the tasks based on the task body presented. Respondents are provided with the following options to choose from:

Very masculine - Rather masculine - Neutral - Rather feminine - Very feminine

Fig. 8. An example question of the questionnaire. (Answers from left to right: very masculine, rather masculine, neutral, rather feminine, very feminine)

In the questionnaire, the participants are given the 2021 and 2022 Junior, Senior Bebras tasks and have to decide whether they considered the tasks to be masculine or feminine based on a quick reading. Participants have to make these quick and intuitive

tive judgements based only on the brief descriptions of the tasks and the associated graphical elements. In this way, the study focuses on exploring how the "gender" of the task will be perceived by the participants through their first impressions.

4 Discussion

The aim of future research on the questionnaire is to determine whether gender perceptions of tasks are synchronous in those tasks where significant differences were found between boys' and girls' scores. If task perceptions show significant differences in perceptions, it is necessary to determine whether this is caused by the text, graphic elements or other cultural preconceptions of the tasks. If necessary, replacing these elements of the tasks by repeating the research will clearly identify what is causing the gender bias. Finally, an international comparison would be undertaken, where we would look at the tasks in different countries, and through this we would investigate the role of linguistic and cultural factors.

A next step – to analyze the results and texting, visual elements of other countries and languages could extend the research.

We believe that the results of our research can greatly help the future design of the Bebras tasks to ensure that the implementation of inclusive task design is not compromised in any way, as one of the most important aspects of the Bebras Initiative is to make information technology accessible to all, creating equal conditions for challenge participants.

Another aspect of the significant difference between the results of girls and boys could show a general problem in science education based on preconceptions of gender roles. A deeper analysis of attitudes and changes of attitudes during school years can be the following research sub-topic. Based on the result of gender motivation research the aspect of the action can have another dimension.

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Appendix

Appendix A – Result of the tasks’ analysis in Hungarian Bebras Challenge 2021 separately:

junior					senior				
	Boys	N=6562	Girls	N=5929		Boys	N=1976	Girls	N=808
task name	mean	sd	mean	sd	task name	mean	sd	mean	sd
2021-AT-01	0,13	0,988	0,11	0,991	2018-LT-04	-0,3	0,82	-0,27	0,804
2021-BE-02	-0,54	0,836	-0,6	0,794	2021-AT-06	-0,48	0,767	-0,37	0,802
2021-CA-02	0,25	0,938	0,3	0,92	2021-BE-02	-0,52	0,844	-0,54	0,837
2021-CH-04c1	0,57	0,816	0,56	0,822	2021-CA-02	0,44	0,883	0,38	0,901
2021-CH-06	0,5	0,857	0,56	0,827	2021-CH-06	0,62	0,775	0,61	0,784
2021-CH-07a	-0,04	0,963	-0,05	0,959	2021-CH-07a	0,02	0,968	0,01	0,97
2021-CH-13	0,04	0,971	0,13	0,965	2021-CH-13	0,19	0,971	0,19	0,968
2021-CZ-05	-0,08	0,986	-0,07	0,991	2021-CZ-04	-0,11	0,95	-0,39	0,848
2021-DE-08b	-0,11	0,98	-0,12	0,98	2021-CZ-05	-0,08	0,985	-0,08	0,986
2021-HU-02	0,58	0,807	0,53	0,839	2021-DE-05	-0,2	0,906	-0,14	0,882
2021-ID-10	0,67	0,717	0,66	0,729	2021-HU-02	0,65	0,752	0,5	0,862
2021-IN-05	0,14	0,976	0,07	0,982	2021-HU-04	-0,31	0,842	-0,39	0,778
2021-IT-01b	-0,34	0,881	-0,34	0,888	2021-ID-10	0,76	0,63	0,67	0,716
2021-LT-07	0,34	0,938	0,31	0,948	2021-IT-01b	-0,21	0,945	-0,22	0,933
2021-PH-03	-0,35	0,896	-0,44	0,854	2021-IT-02b	-0,36	0,84	-0,4	0,785
2021-SI-02	-0,25	0,925	-0,33	0,895	2021-PH-03	-0,34	0,916	-0,46	0,855
2021-SV-01	0,17	0,959	0,09	0,967	2021-SI-02	-0,04	0,972	-0,24	0,922
2021-UZ-02	0,02	0,995	-0,07	0,993	2021-SV-01	0,27	0,949	0,14	0,973

id	junior	senior
2018-LT-04		no sign.dif.
2021-AT-01	no sign.dif.	
2021-AT-06		Z=-3.585; p<=.001
2021-BE-02	Z=-4.492; p<.001	no sign.dif.
2021-CA-02	Z= -2.926; p=.003	no sign.dif.
2021-CH-04c1	no sign.dif.	
2021-CH-06	Z= -3.572; p<.001	no sign.dif.
2021-CH-07a	no sign.dif.	no sign.dif.
2021-CH-13	Z= -5.036; p<.001	no sign.dif.
2021-CZ-04		Z= -6.916; p<.001
2021-CZ-05	no sign.dif.	no sign.dif.
2021-DE-03		
2021-DE-05		no sign.dif.
2021-DE-08b	no sign.dif.	
2021-HU-02	Z= -3.091; p=.002	Z= -4.784; p<.001
2021-HU-04		no sign.dif.
2021-ID-10	no sign.dif.	Z= -3.287; p=.001
2021-IN-05	Z= -4.372; p<.001	
2021-IT-01b	no sign.dif.	no sign.dif.
2021-IT-02b		no sign.dif.
2021-LT-07	no sign.dif.	
2021-PH-03	Z= -5.354; p<.001	Z= -2.997; p=.003
2021-SI-02	Z= -4.120; p<.001	Z= -4.868; p<.001
2021-SV-01	Z= -4.585; p<.001	Z= -3.192; p=.001
2021-UZ-02	Z= -4.733; p<.001	

Appendix B – Result of the tasks’ analysis in Hungarian Bebras Challenge 2022 separately:

	junior				senior				
	Boys	N=6562	Girls	N=5929		Boys	N=1976	Girls	N=808
task name	mean	sd	mean	sd	task name	mean	sd	mean	sd
2022-AU-03	0.83	0.545	0.73	0.675	2022-AT-04	0.06	0.972	0.04	0.956
2022-CA-06	0.27	0.956	0.15	0.98	2022-CH-04	-0.03	0.963	-0.21	0.937
2022-CY-01	0.31	0.946	0.35	0.929	2022-DE-03	0.57	0.785	0.47	0.83

2022-HU-04	-0.29	0.944	-0.62	0.759	2022-DE-05	-0.39	0.901	-0.5	0.828
2022-SK-04	0.45	0.883	0.44	0.886	2022-DE-07	-0.67	0.722	-0.69	0.698
2022-VN-05b	0.24	0.961	0.26	0.956	2022-LV-03	-0.09	0.986	-0.22	0.956
2022-AT-04	-0.11	0.953	-0.18	0.931	2022-CA-04	-0.31	0.936	-0.44	0.879
2022-CH-04	-0.03	0.965	-0.23	0.933	2022-IT-02	-0.4	0.893	-0.4	0.89
2022-DE-03	0.51	0.806	0.41	0.855	2022-MK-01	-0.04	0.98	-0.04	0.979
2022-DE-05	-0.43	0.872	-0.52	0.794	2022-NL-03	0	0.024	0	0
2022-DE-07	-0.73	0.634	-0.79	0.568	2022-US-06	-0.21	0.913	-0.27	0.892
2022-LV-03	-0.23	0.942	-0.33	0.907	2022-UZ-03	-0.1	0.944	-0.28	0.896
2022-CA-04	-0.38	0.882	-0.52	0.805	2022-AT-02	-0.3	0.864	-0.36	0.842
2022-IT-02	-0.47	0.821	-0.48	0.818	2022-BE-02	0.08	0.911	0.14	0.903
2022-MK-01	-0.24	0.9	-0.31	0.882	2022-CA-02	-0.31	0.821	-0.3	0.825
2022-NL-03	0	0.032	0	0.018	2022-KR-06	-0.51	0.617	-0.53	0.582
2022-US-06	-0.14	0.872	-0.15	0.872	2022-NZ-01	-0.63	0.535	-0.62	0.506
2022-UZ-03	-0.19	0.864	-0.29	0.841	2022-UA-03b	-0.47	0.53	-0.44	0.533

id	junior	senior
2022-AT-02		no sign.dif.
2022-AT-04	Z=-3.753; p<.001	no sign.dif.
2022-AU-03	Z=-9.879; p<.001	
2022-BE-02		no sign.dif.
2022-CA-02		no sign.dif.
2022-CA-04	Z=-9.293; p<.001	Z=-5.196; p<.001
2022-CA-06	Z=-7.047; p<.001	
2022-CH-04	Z=-11.723; p<.001	Z=-6.881; p<.001
2022-CY-01	Z=-2.793; p=.005	
2022-DE-03	Z=-7.418; p<.001	Z=-4.837; p<.001
2022-DE-05	Z=-5.461; p<.001	Z=-4.011; p<.001
2022-DE-07	Z=-4.972; p<.001	no sign.dif.
2022-HU-04	Z=-20.689; p<.001	
2022-IT-02	no sign.dif.	no sign.dif.
2022-KR-06		no sign.dif.
2022-LV-03	Z=-6.450; p<.001	Z=-4.693; p<.001
2022-MK-01	Z=-4.479; p<.001	no sign.dif.
2022-NL-03	no sign.dif.	no sign.dif.
2022-NZ-01		no sign.dif.
2022-SK-04	no sign.dif.	
2022-UA-03b		no sign.dif.
2022-US-06	no sign.dif.	no sign.dif.
2022-UZ-03	Z=-6.523; p<.001	Z=-6.715; p<.001
2022-VN-05b	no sign.dif.	